

COLONIALISM VS RESISTANCE; AN ANALYSIS OF SELECTED POST COLONIAL TEXTS UNDER THE THEORETICAL UNDERPINNINGS OF POST COLONIAL NOTION

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ABSTRACT

This research analyzes the significant and far-reaching effects of colonization on the postcolonial literature, focusing passive resistance particularly. Through a directed qualitative content analysis, following the framework proposed by Hsieh and Shannon, (2005), this article profoundly analyzes four pieces of postcolonial literature, focusing the multidimensional impacts of colonialism upon the culture, psyche and society of the colonized individuals. This study explores the major themes of postcolonial literature including marginalization, identity crisis, linguistic imperialism and depression among some others. This research aims to expand our knowledge about the postcolonial literature, and how the people of that time resisted the power centers. Ultimately, this article contributes to the present body of research in elaborating the influences of colonialism on the postcolonial literature.

Keywords: Colonialism, Postcolonial literature, Resistance.

INTRODUCTION

The process of colonialism, which lasted for centuries and covered a major portion of the world, has influenced the literature ineradicably. The word "postcolonialism" has a dual meaning with two root words, "post" and "colonial". The first meaning refers to the old chronological thought, which is "after colonialism". On the other hand, the second meaning portrays a more philosophical idea, that denotes a time beyond colonialism. (Graham et al., 2012) Postcolonialism, a critical and theoretical approach that developed in the mid-20th century, analyzes and interrogates the changes in culture, complex power dynamics, and identity crisis that are produced due to colonial encounters. The colonialism has deeply molded the way people write, read and unveil the literature, transforming the intended meaning into a reflection of the impacts of colonialism on them, showing their resistance through the literature.

If we extract the essence of postcolonialism, it actually focuses at the ways in which the colonial powers have influenced the cultural, social and economic areas of the colonized societies. It presents how the colonizers imposed their languages, values, and education systems on the helpless colonized people, often violently. This behavior pressurized the colonized ones to induce the colonizers' language, forgetting to keep their cultural values. Resultantly, the postcolonial literature tried to reconstitute these lost narratives, presenting the impacts of colonization in their community after a long period of suppression. Dizayi, (2017) comments that the postcolonial literature presents the struggles of the colonized people for defining their true self and culture. Due to the conflict with opposing culture of the powerful colonizers, self-defining became challenging for the marginalized individuals.

The postcolonial literature has vital importance, as it is a significant mean of expressing resistance and the sorrows regarding this period using fictions as a shield. The writers from the formerly targeted region share their experiences aesthetically. Their works function as their weapon against the dominant colonial narratives, presenting their real cultures, histories and identities. According to Nayar (2008), the postcolonial literature presents exploitation, inequality and oppression. The postcolonial literature portrays the themes including identity crisis, marginalization, depression, mimicry, and resistance. The literature uses narratives, language and symbols to challenge the dominant discourses, and share personal experiences in unique and innovative style. Dar (2019) analyzes that colonialism is about the differences in power between the colonizers and the colonized. He highlights some countries like Africa, Pakistan, India, Somalia, and Australia, and says that the ideologies and cultures of these regions were greatly affected by colonization. He comments upon their literature by saying that they have expressing resistance through their writings, and they have presented the true face of the colonizers who suppressed them through violence.

By studying the postcolonial literature, the audience gets a thought-provoking and revelatory lens, which makes the examination of the identities and cultures of the postcolonial world more authentic. The postcolonial literature depicts the brutal experiences of the colonized people and their struggles to keep their identities by portraying the major themes, such as hybridity, racial discrimination, identity formation, and cultural dominance (Thamarana, 2015). According to a research, the postcolonial literature encompasses a wide range of themes, such as resistance, cultural hybridity, identity, struggles for independence, self-definition, etc. (Kalyani et al., 2023). The analysis of the works of these writers will help shaping our understanding about the history. By the close reading of the selected works, we would be able to demonstrate how the postcolonial literature portrays the colonial history and its impacts.

1.1. Problem Statement:

During the recent years, significant attention has been gained by the realm of postcolonial literature by the scholars. While several studies

have analyzed the broader impacts of colonialism, there was a need to examine some particular literary works that illustrate the implications of colonialism over characters' emotional and mental state. This research paper explores identity crisis, depression, ambiguity, the negative impacts of colonization on characters and some other important and related ideas through some selected works from postcolonial literature, filling the gap. This research delves into the themes of emotional and physical wellbeing of the colonized people, and the passive resistance by them. This paper is limited to the analysis of a specific literary works. This study helps in providing a deeper understanding of the impacts of colonization on the literature of postcolonial era.

1.2. Research Gap:

The previous researches have significantly contributed to the study of postcolonial literature, but insufficient attention has been paid to the nuanced examination of specific literary works that would provide a better understanding of the postcolonial experience. Through the analysis of a particular pieces from literature, this research will present the impacts of colonialism on individuals through characters. Moreover, this research focuses on more than one works from the postcolonial literature. Furthermore, this paper will also concentrate another gap, which is the limited attention paid towards the emotional and mental disturbance of individuals and their passive resistance. It highlights the negative impacts of colonization over the individuals, portrayed through the postcolonial literature. This study adds more to the existing knowledge of postcolonial literature.

1.3. Research Objective:

To explore how the themes of postcolonial literature portray the influence of colonialism on the literary body, and how the characters passively resisted the scenario.

1.4. Research Question:

How did the themes of postcolonial literature portray the influence of colonialism on the literary body, and how the characters passively resisted the scenario?

1.5. Significance:

This study has a great importance in the realm of postcolonial literature, as it works upon unveiling the multiple, intricate impacts of colonization on the postcolonial literary writings. After a thorough analysis of some specific literary works, this work explores the role of colonialism in shaping the individual and collective identities. This research significantly takes part in adding more to the existing knowledge of postcolonial literature.

The focus of this study on some specific literary texts enables an elaborate and deep examination of the complex impacts of colonialism on the literature. By focusing some important motifs, this analysis provides a nuanced understanding of the literature of that era. This article highlights the characteristics of colonialism that can be seen in the postcolonial literature, like patriarchy and double oppression on women, conflicts between the dominant and marginalized traditions and cultures, resistance towards the central colonial narratives, mimicry, identity crisis or self-doubt, imperialism, misogyny, hegemony and many more, mainly through magical realism. This study also reveals the impacts of colonization on individual and collective lives through the analysis of characters of the novels, and the marginalization by the power centers.

Moreover, this analysis would help in the comprehensive and intricate understanding of the postcolonial literature. It also portrays how identities were shaped, cultures were exchanged and the globalization occurred at that time. This study contributes into the previous knowledge, assisting the research body to grow more. Furthermore, it activates the empathy among the audience for the postcolonial world, highlighting their complex experiences.

1.6. Limitations:

Although this article portrays the impacts of colonization on postcolonial literature, but still there are some limitations. The major, pivotal issue is that the study is limited to some specific literary works, which may not be able to portray the entire postcolonial literary corpus. This research focuses the texts according to their relevance to the question. However, the other literary works may have portrayed a different idea.

Additionally, this research is confined to a particular historical context, which is the time after colonization or the postcolonial era. The study may also be affected by the researcher's personal biases, based upon the cultural or historical backgrounds. However, this paper still contributes a lot in the understanding of postcolonial literature. The future research can be based upon other literary works, with unique themes and contexts, analyzed through a different lens or theoretical framework and an alternate methodology.

2. Theoretical Framework:

The theoretical foundation of this research is based upon the Reader-Response Theory, in which the reader plays his active role in the analysis and meaning creation of the texts. The pioneers of this theory were Stanley Fish (1980) and Wolfgang Iser (1974). According to them, the meaning of a literary text is not permanent, but rather is creatively decided by the reader. As this research meant to analyze some subjective literary works from postcolonial time, the researcher adopted this theory to deviate from the authors' point of view, and analyze the texts from the reader's perspective. By sharing the personal perspectives and experiences, the researcher can provide a better insight and nuanced appreciation of the related portrayals in the texts.

3. Literature Review:

Colonization practiced profound imperialism over the colonized people, exerting violence upon their psyche, shaping their thought or mindset. This brutal and pervasive form of hegemony dragged the people into identity crisis, where people struggled for the reconciliation of their indigenous identities, norms, values and culture. Resultantly, the colonized individuals responded in a quiet despair and passive resistance. This literature review pursues to grasp the impacts of the complexities of that period through the analysis of some texts from the postcolonial literature.

3.1. Jean Rhys's *Wide Sargasso Sea*:

The novel "*Wide Sargasso Sea*" by Jean Rhys is an important work of postcolonial era, published in 1966. In this novel, the character of "Bertha (previously Antoinette)", the wife of Mr.

Rochester depicts the marginalization of women by a patriarchal society during postcolonial era. Senel (2014) states that Rhys has portrayed the character of the psychologically sick Bertha to present the reasons behind her madness, which include her suffering of double oppression. He says that the patriarchal society controls and limits her agency and makes her mad, which is a kind of resistance from her. This insanity of the protagonist leads her to be a victim of identity crisis, racial and patriarchal oppression, feeling of insecurity, distrust, and lack of belonging. The researcher also refers to Gayatri Spivak's concept of subalternity and confesses that a subaltern cannot speak, and if he tries to resist, it will result into madness. It shows how much cruel the oppressive powers are, who do not let an individual live a healthy life according to his personal desires. Her character also portrays hybridity and fragmented identity, as she was caught between her black Caribbean roots and her white European heritage. She felt into identity crisis and was accepted by none of both. Her marriage also portrayed how the will of women were neglected even if it was about their own future or fortune. Azam (2017) comments that Antoinette had a mixed racial background which made her an "other" in both West Indian and European societies. She struggled to get an identity in either, but was caught between both ideologies. Moreover, her marriage to Rochester disintegrated her sense of self, as he wanted her to be what he wants. Initially, he perceived her as a beautiful woman, but later when she tries to become rational insanely, he starts detesting her. At that time, madness becomes a way of passive resistance for her to feel alive, providing her a sense of control and power. It presents that the people of that era had grown mad, not because they had any medical problems, but they practiced madness as a coping mechanism. Those isolated and controlled individuals felt it a way of self-expression and agency. The ultimate death of the protagonist proves that the people of that era struggled to escape the scenario, as they were disturbed mentally.

Overall, this novel is a literary gem by Jean Rhys, that challenges the dominant colonial narratives of patriarchy. It masterfully highlights the depressing experiences of women of the postcolonial societies, and the need for their resistance and escape.

3.2. Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*:

The novel "Things Fall Apart" by Chinua Achebe, published in 1958, is an influential novel from the postcolonial literature that highlights the influence of the colonization on the cultures and traditions of African society. Thamarana (2015) says that the British colonizers always tried to weaken the united countries to the possible extent. In accordance to his point of view, this novel also presents that the united, culturally rich Igbo community is ruined because of the colonization. The major character of the novel, Okonkwo was an esteemed warrior and leader of Igbo, Umuofia. He struggles to uphold his culture and traditions amidst the chaos of British intrusion in their society. The novel also portrays the conflicts between the British colonizers and the Igbo people, where people resisted the impositions of the colonizers due to the cultural clash. Salami (2018) exposes the adverse aspects of the colonial powers that they lack empathy and get curious towards complex human tragedies. He analyzed this shortcoming through the character of the district officer who considered the death of Okonkwo as the best script for his book. This characteristic develops a stark boundary between the colonizers and the colonized people. Okonkwo also faces identity crisis when his own Igbo community pushes him out of their society. His character also portrays resistance toward the colonization and the destructive outcomes of resisting imperialism in the face of his ultimate demise. Walder (2010) states that Achebe has wonderfully challenged the stereotype attached to the African society that they are savages. His narrative brought an absurd situation for the readers, where they began doubting the colonial narratives. He skillfully redefines the scenario from the perspective of the colonized people. He has subverted the stereotypes. Alam (2014) appreciates Achebe for presenting the authentic picture of the African culture, and giving voice to the misrepresented and silenced people. This novel skillfully portrays the struggles of the weak colonized communities in protecting their cultural values, and resisting the colonial powers.

3.3. Derek Walcott's *Dream on a Monkey Mountain*:

The play "Dream on Monkey Mountain" by Derek Walcott, published in 1970, explores the

intricacies of identity, politics and culture during postcolonial era. As a critique to colonialism in the Caribbean region, the author portrays the character of Makak, who is suffering from identity crisis. Torres (2020) comments that Makak desired to go back to Africa, which shows that a person cannot disconnect himself from his cultural roots. However, the colonization induced self-hatred in Makak, which lead him to doubt his identity and call himself a monkey. The real name of Makak was Felix Hobain, but due to his inner turmoil, he claimed that he is Makak, which means “Monkey” in Haitian Creole. He considered himself an animal because of the induced class difference between him and the colonizers. Abd-Aun (2015) asserts that Walcott has presented internalized inferiority complex through the character of Makak, who is psychologically captured by the colonial powers. It shows hegemony, practiced by the colonizers. Hunter (2007) states that racial discrimination and marginalization of the Africans by the colonizers had a great impact upon their emotional health. The mental disturbance of Makak proves that the poor Africans had a feeling of inferiority that he tried to overcome by mimicking the colonizers. Alam et al., (2020) comments that this novel of Derek Walcott portrays despair, fear and inferiority as its major themes. These were the key ideas that were introduced into the minds of the colonized people by the colonizers. Moreover, the people of that era wished to escape that depressing scenario, which can be seen through Makak’s character, who escaped into fantasy, portraying the difficulty to confront the reality. Escaping was a way of resistance for the colonized people. This work from the postcolonial literature presents the desires of the colonized people through the character of Makak, who longs for liberation and self-determination. (Rehman et al., 2024). Conclusively, this play is a beautiful portrayal of the scenario of postcolonial period. It helps the readers to contemplate critically and shape his knowledge of the impacts of colonialism.

3.4. Wole Soyinka’s *A Dance of the Forest*:

The play “A Dance of the Forest” by Wole Soyinka, published in 1963, is a rich and complex work portraying the postcolonial Nigeria. Tessa (2014) says that Soyinka has portrayed the colonial imperialism and their imposition of

language on the colonized individuals, suppressing their native language and culture. This linguistic imperialism was a mean of the cultural erasure of the oppressed colonized individuals, which lead them to resist the colonial powers. Anyokwu (2012) observes that Wole Soyinka has written the play in English language, which is a symbol that the colonizers have imposed their language in that region. Meanwhile, the chaos presented in the play presents the disorder and unrest in the society during postcolonial era. Di Fabio (2016) says that the colonial powers induced the ideology that the people who embrace changes can more easily adopt modernity. They do not consider it a challenge for the colonized individuals to follow the imposed culture and neglect their own. This play explores the complications of switching your personality. Soyinka highlights the corruption by the power centers, as they misuse their authority and violate the rights of the colonized people. There was no justice during the postcolonial period, so the author skillfully presents the idea of retribution in the life hereafter. Soyinka portrays the idea of the cyclic nature of oppression and violence through the theme of death. It presents how the bad deeds of the past continue to haunt your present. Monika (2025) mentions that Soyinka’s work is based upon magical realism, as it portrays the reality of echoing chaos during postcolonial period through surrealism and imagery. It means that reading the play will help the audience realize the unjust, corrupt and chaotic situation of the era. Tessa (2014) critiques that Soyinka has portrayed a cruel and manipulative picture of women through the character of Rola, making her a prostitute. It presents that the writers of that era were also under the influence of misogyny. The patriarchal society abused women. Meanwhile, they detested women. According to a research, the postcolonial literature presents the moral ambiguity of the individuals through characters, just like Soyinka has portrayed the character of Demoke, who presented self-expression and creativity as he was an artist, but at the same time, he was a murderer. (Farahbakhsh et al., 2017). It depicts that colonialism disseminated ambivalence and aggression in the society. David et al., (2009) says that unity brings peace and satisfaction. Soyinka portrayed the characters who committed crimes in their first life and are

facing the consequences in their afterlife. It is because they did not have any collective experience, that could shape their decision-making and group behavior. The researcher says that if they had been living unitedly, they could have a happy life. It portrays the idea that the colonizers and the colonized people should have lived together by cooperating with each other, without creating a boundary of class difference. Abdel Fattah (2016) states that Soyinka has claimed that the society was free from most social evils and it was living extremely happy, before the intrusion of the Europeans. He says that the current social evils are also an impact of the colonization. This multidimensional play by Wole Soyinka masterfully depicts the complexity of the postcolonial period.

4. Research Methodology:

This research follows the directed qualitative method of analysis to explore the influence of colonization on the postcolonial literature. The framework proposed by Hsieh and Shannon, (2005) is followed for the content analysis. The methodology is designed in accordance with the purpose of thematic analysis.

4.1. Data Collection:

The postcolonial or the decolonization era spans between 1950s to 1980s. Therefore, the data is collected through the analysis of four literary texts, published between 1955-1970. These pieces of literature portray how colonialism affected the postcolonial literature. The selection of these texts was based upon their relevance with the research question.

4.2. Sample Size:

This research highlights the important postcolonial themes through the selection of four literary works, scripted by different authors.

4.3. Research Design and Data Analysis:

This research is designed for the qualitative content analysis. The process of analyzing data involves the close reading of the texts selected to identify the important themes of the time. The data analysis process is guided by the Reader-Response Theory.

4.4. Sampling Strategy:

This research employed the purposive sampling approach. The literary texts were selected according to their relevance to the question and context of this research. So, the purposive sampling allows to select the texts that are the most relevant.

4.5. Research Tools:

This study uses the techniques of close reading and note-taking for the examination of the selected literary texts through the qualitative content analysis.

5. Results and Discussion:

This study has significantly depicted the influences of colonization on the depressed colonized people. This research has highlighted multiple themes that define the particular era and its brutal impacts upon the people. Through the characters in the texts, the experiences of the colonized people have been shared, portraying the real picture of colonization and its effects. The theme of double oppression of women is portrayed through the "Wide Sargasso Sea", where the women not only suffer by impacts of colonization, but also bear patriarchy. It shows the suppression of women during postcolonial era. Moreover, this novel portrays the idea that madness as a form passive resistance is a consequence of oppressive colonialism.

In addition, "Things Fall Apart" by Chinua Achebe presents how the colonial powers through their dominant narratives portrayed a negative picture and stereotypes attached to the colonizers, although they themselves were the authoritative oppressors. They forcefully molded the cultures and traditions of the colonized people, who in return resisted the power centers through different techniques. In this play, the characters openly initiated a war with the Britishers.

Furthermore, Derek Walcott's "Dream on Monkey Mountain" portrays inferiority complex and identity crisis propagated in the society by the colonizers by internalized oppression. This play also portrays hegemony, as Makak subconsciously wanted to be like the colonizers, when he declared that he was a king. He escaped his real self and claimed that he is Makak, the King. It was also a way of passive resistance.

Last but not the least, the play “A Dance of the Forests” by Wole Soyinka displays the themes including linguistic imperialism, lack of unity, misogyny and corruption. This play masterfully highlights the complexities of living in an unjust world and the consequences of criminal activities in the world hereafter. It can be message from the writer to the dominant narratives that the misuse of power will not be forgiven. The play also portrays the misinterpretation of women due to misogyny.

Ultimately, this research explores the unique perspectives of four literary works from the postcolonial literature. The themes present in these works define the postcolonial era clearly. Moreover, all the four novels portray passive resistance through the characters, who symbolize the individuals of that era.

6. Conclusion:

The postcolonial literature displays the deep and profound impacts of colonization on the individuals, who were involved into passive resistance that emerged as a reaction to the colonial rule and oppression. The discussed canon of literature portrays the multifaceted impacts of colonization, including personal identity struggle, where the individuals strive to either protect their identity or mimic the colonizers’ identity. The induced inferiority complex which is a major characteristic of colonialism is one of the dominant themes of the postcolonial literature. It is due to their, background, race or culture. Moreover, the linguistic imperialism by the colonizers imposes the foreign language on the colonized people, threatening their native languages and culture. Some other themes like the marginalization of women, lack of unity and the prevalence of corruption are also prominent in the postcolonial literature, depicting the adverse effects of the colonialism. Ultimately, the postcolonial literature also presents depression, escapism, emotional distress, sufferings, death, and many more, portraying a nuanced and authentic knowledge of the lasting impacts of colonialism.

REFERENCES:

Nayar, P. K. (2008). *Postcolonial Literature: an introduction*. Pearson Education India.

- Dizayi, S. A. H. (2017). The crisis of identity in postcolonial literature. *Journal of Advanced Research in Social Sciences*, 2(1), 79-86.
- Thamarana, S. (2015). Significance of studying postcolonial literature and its relevance. *Research Journal of English Language and Literature*, 3(3), 537-541.
- Graham, J., Niblett, M., & Deckard, S. (2012). Postcolonial studies and world literature. *Journal of Postcolonial Writing*, 48(5), 465-471.
- Dar, B. A. (2019). Postcolonial literature: A definitive and analytical study. *International Journal of English Research*, 5(3), 34-36.
- Kalyani, E. R., & Jyothi, L. *Voices Across Borders: Exploring the Depth of Postcolonial Literature*.
- Senel, N. (2014). A Postcolonial Reading of *Wide Sargasso Sea* by Jean Rhys. *Dil ve Edebiyat Egitimi Dergisi*, 2(11), 38.
- Azam, N. (2017). “Madwoman in the Post-Colonial Era” A Study of the Female Voice in Jean Rhys’ *Wide Sargasso Sea*. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 6(7), 236-242.
- Walder, D. (2010). *Postcolonial nostalgias: writing, representation and memory*. Routledge.
- Salami, A., & Shoar, B. H. (2018). Things fall apart and Chinua Achebe’s postcolonial discourse.
- Alam, M. (2014). Reading Chinua Achebe’s *Things Fall Apart* from the Postcolonial Perspective. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4.
- Rahman, Z. U., Ali, S., & Ullah, I. (2024). The Quest for Identity Conciliation and Racial Harmony: Postcolonial Critique of Mohsin Hamid’s *the Last White Man* and Derek Walcott’s *Dream on Monkey Mountain*. *Al-Mahdi Research Journal (MRJ)*, 5(3), 1073-1087.
- Tessa, Z. (2014). *JM Synge’s The Shadow of the Glen and Wole Soyinka’s A Dance of the Forests: A Postcolonial Study* (Doctoral dissertation, university Mouloud Mammeri of Tizi-Ouzou).

- Farahbakhsh, A., & Sheykhan, R. R. (2017). Ambivalent Identity in Wole Soyinka's A Dance of the Forests.
- Di Fabio, A., & Gori, A. (2016). Developing a new instrument for assessing acceptance of change. *Frontiers in psychology*, 7, 802.
- David, O., & Bar-Tal, D. (2009). A sociopsychological conception of collective identity: The case of national identity as an example. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 13(4), 354-379.
- Abdel Fattah, A. (2016). Postcolonial Identity in Soyinka's A Dance of the Forests and the Road. *المجلة العلمية لكلية الآداب-جامعة أسبوت*, 19(58), 8-36.
- Anyokwu, C. (2012). Ode to Chaos and Amnesia: Fractured Narrative and Heteroglossia as Postcolonial Othering in Wole Soyinka's A Dance of the Forests. *Nordic Journal of African Studies*, 21(1), 15-15.
- Monika, (2025) retrieved from Monika, K., & Meenakshi, S. Dance of the Forests, retrieved on June 22, 2025.
- Torres, G. E. V. (2020). Staging the Scars of Colonialism: No Escape for Characters of Caribbean Drama (Master's thesis, University of Puerto Rico, Rio Piers (Puerto Rico)).
- Abd-Aun, R. K. (2015) Loss and Recovery of Identity in Derek Walcott's Dream on Monkey Mountain.
- Alam, K., & Akhtar, R. (2020). Hybrid Aesthetics and Politics of Resistance; Re-inventing the Western Dramatic Form in Derek Walcott's Dream on Monkey Mountain. *Journal of the Research Society of Pakistan-Vol. No, 57(1)*.
- Hunter, M. (2007). The persistent problem of colorism: Skin tone, status, and inequality. *Sociology compass*, 1(1), 237-254.

